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Amitava Roy, Ronan Paterson,
Bryan Reynolds, Subir Dhar, Papia Mitra

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**Subir Dhar, Ronan Paterson,
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ASSESSING THE INTEGRATED TEACHER EDUCATION PROGRAM (ITEP): A STUDY ON PERCEPTION AMONG FACULTY IN DELHI/NCR

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Abstract

The Integrated Teacher Education Program (ITEP), implemented as part of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, aims to bring about a transformative change in teacher education in India. This study assesses the perspectives of faculty members in the Delhi/NCR region on ITEP execution. Data were collected using a self-administered questionnaire that included several aspects of ITEP, based on a descriptive survey of 40 faculty members of a teacher education institution. The results suggest that there is a generally positive evaluation of the advantages of ITEP, which encompass enhancing the efficiency of the preparation process and offering increased career adaptability for preservice teachers. However, there are concerns about the accessibility of teachers and resources, the structure of the curriculum, financial limitations, administrative difficulties, and the evaluation of the program. These findings emphasize the importance of consistently improving ITEP implementation to tackle problems and optimize its capacity to advance teacher education. Policymakers and educators should utilize these insights to optimize the effectiveness of ITEP and ensure that it is in line with the changing requirements of the education sector in India. Additional research is recommended to investigate methods to overcome identified obstacles and improve the efficacy of ITEP.

Keyword: *ITEP, Teacher Education, National Education Policy, NCTE*

INTRODUCTION

The Integrated Teacher Education Program (ITEP) is a substantial overhaul of teacher education put forth by the National Council of Teacher Education (NCTE) under the Ministry of Education, India, as a component of the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020. The objective of this study is to evaluate the perception of faculty members in the Delhi/NCR region on ITEP implementation. The teaching profession generally emphasizes professionalism to strengthen its reputation and improve the quality of service (Hoyle, 2001). Sachs (2003) identified external forces, public discourse, and scientific breakthroughs as variables that influence the formation of teacher professionalism. Likewise, the issues mentioned above have an impact on teacher education policies and programs in Indian higher education.

ITEP offers a comprehensive undergraduate education program that includes specialized concentrations in subjects such as language, history, mathematics, and other disciplines. The new educational framework of the 2020 National Education Policy (NEP) is in line with the design of the curriculum. The program's objective, as stated in the National Education Policy of 2020, is to provide instruction to educators at all educational levels, combining Indian values with contemporary pedagogical advancements (Ministry of Education, 2020). However, some challenges must be overcome to effectively implement ITEP. Educational institutions must engage in thorough planning and preparation to ensure seamless implementation of the curriculum. However, the curriculum was established to streamline teacher education and optimize students' time in their academic endeavors. Padwad and Dixit (2014) argue that the successful implementation of ITEP requires making essential changes to the infrastructure, providing training to the faculty, and ensuring compliance with national standards.

Additionally, the way faculty members are seen plays a crucial role in determining the effectiveness of the ITEP for the organization. The fact that they are familiar with the curriculum, the methods of instruction, and the challenges that are encountered in the actual world can provide politicians and institutions with vital information about the potential hurdles and the necessary adjustments. Faculty involvement and support are crucial for establishing the program's legitimacy and long-term viability. Institutional preparedness is of the utmost importance for successfully implementing ITEP. To effectively address the issues brought about by the transition, it is imperative to have sufficient preparation in terms of faculty development, curriculum alignment, and infrastructure enhancement.

Furthermore, ongoing support and feedback methods are necessary to improve the program and address new problems (Chudgar, 2013).

Assessing the opinions of faculty members on the Integrated Teacher Education Program (ITEP) in Delhi/NCR is crucial to evaluate its effectiveness and identify any challenges and prospects it presents. To improve the content and teaching methods of ITEP, policymakers and schools can benefit from aggressively soliciting the viewpoints of faculty members. Additionally, including professors in the evaluation process promotes active participation and dedication to the program, thereby guaranteeing its efficient execution and long-term sustainability. The study's findings support evidence-based policymaking. They will contribute to the development of future strategies for teacher training and ensure that educational initiatives align with the evolving demands of the education industry. Ultimately, this leads to an improvement in the quality of education in India.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. Examine the perceived advantages of ITEP.
2. To evaluate the difficulties in the implementation of the Integration of Teacher Education Program (ITEP) about:
 - 2.1. Availability of faculty and infrastructure resources
 - 2.2. Design of curriculum and program
 - 2.3. Financial factors to be considered.
 - 2.4. Collaborations between internships and educational institutions
 - 2.5. Challenges related to administration.
 - 2.6. Evaluation

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section covers details about sampling, data collection tools and techniques, and analysis.

SAMPLE

It is a descriptive study aiming to collect data on faculty perceptions such as professor, associate professor, assistant professor, lecturer, and research scholars of the Integrated Teacher Education Program (ITEP). To gain a comprehensive understanding of ITEPs, this study employed a convenience sampling method to choose forty faculty, i.e. ten each from the professor, associate professor, and assistant professor and five each from lecturer and research scholars, from an institution of teacher education in Delhi/NCR.

TOOL AND TECHNIQUE

Data were obtained using a self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed according to the objectives of the study. The poll comprised 37 items that were assessed using a 5-point Likert scale, spanning from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree." Specifically, there were a total of five inquiries about benefits, four inquiries about faculty and resources, six inquiries about infrastructure and resources, seven inquiries about the design curriculum and program, three inquiries each regarding financial considerations, internship and school partnerships, and administrative challenges, and finally six inquiries about ITEP evaluation. Data were obtained from faculty members through a survey method.

ANALYSIS

The survey data were analyzed using Jamovi software. The acquired data will be used to calculate the mean, mode and median individually. Furthermore, the standard deviation is used to assess the level of consistency among the responses.

FINDINGS

The tables provided present frequencies and percentages of various designations, teaching experiences, and genders among a group of individuals, likely within an academic context such as a university or research institution.

Table 1
Frequencies of Designation

Designation	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
Research Scholar	5	13 %	13 %
Lecturer	5	13 %	25 %
Assistant Professor	10	25 %	50 %
Associate Professor	10	25 %	75 %
Professor	10	25 %	100 %

Table 1 shows the distribution of the designations among the individuals surveyed. The majority of the respondents are Assistant Professors, Associate Professors, and Professors, comprising 25%, 25%, and 25% of the total, respectively. Research Scholars and Lecturers each make up 13% of the total.

Table 2
Frequencies of Teaching experience(s)

Teaching experience(s)	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
NA	4	10 %	10 %
BELOW 5 YEARS	8	20 %	30 %
5-10 YEARS	9	23 %	53 %
11-15 YEARS	9	23 %	75 %
ABOVE 15 YEARS	10	25 %	100 %

Table 2 provides information on the teaching experiences of the respondents. The largest proportion of the respondents, representing 25%, have teaching experience of over 15 years. Following this, 23% have teaching experience in the range of 11-15 years and 5-10 years each, while 20% have below 5 years of teaching experience. Interestingly, 10% of the respondents have no teaching experience, denoted as "NA" in the table.

Table 3
Frequencies of Gender

Gender	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
MALE	24	60 %	60 %
FEMALE	16	40 %	100 %

In addition to this, Table 3 shows the gender distribution among the respondents. The majority, accounting for 60%, are male, while 40% are female.

Table 4
Benefits of ITEP

Items	Mean	Median	Mode	SD
The Integrated Teacher Education Program is an innovative endeavor in the realm of teacher education.	2.83	3.00	3.00	1.38
ITEP enables individuals to pursue a career in teaching based on their personal preferences.	4.00	4.00	4.00	0.82

Table 4
Benefits of ITEP

Items	Mean	Median	Mode	SD
ITEP significantly reduces the amount of time required for preservice teachers to prepare.	4.08	4.00	4.00	0.80
ITEP provides a state-of-the-art level of professionalism comparable to other programs	3.08	3.00	5.00	1.54
ITEP offers a Dual-Liberal Bachelor's Degree	2.88	3.00	1.00	1.45
Overall,,,,,,	3.37	4.00	4.00	1.35

Table 4 presents the benefits of the integrated teacher education Program (ITEP). The initial statement suggests that the respondents perceive ITEP as a distinctive undertaking in teacher education, with an average score of 2.83. The median and mode of the responses are both 3.00, indicating that the respondents have relatively neutral perceptions. However, there is some variety in the responses, as indicated by the standard deviation of 1.38. The respondents agreed that ITEP for enabling individuals to pursue a teaching career aligned with their personal preferences, as indicated by a mean score of 4.00, with both the median and the mode also at 4.00, the standard deviation (0.82) also indicating strong agreement between the respondents. Similarly, ITEP is perceived as significantly reducing the time required for pre-service teachers to prepare, with a mean score of 4.08 and a mode of 4.00, and the standard deviation value (0.80) suggesting a high level of agreement among respondents. However, the respondents were generally neutral in their perception of ITEP providing a state-of-the-art level of professionalism comparable to other programs with a mean score of 3.08 and a median score of 3.00. However, the values of mode (5.00) and SD (1.54) also indicate some variability and disagreement among respondents. The average score for the item related to ITEP's Dual-Liberal Bachelor's Degree offering is 2.88, with a median of 1.00. Respondents had ambivalent or uncertain feelings about this characteristic, as evidenced by a standard deviation of 1.45. The average score for all combined questions is 3.37, suggesting that respondents generally agree with their opinions on ITEP. The median and mode of 4.00 indicate that the general perceptions of ITEP are favourable, while there is some variation in opinions, especially with the level of professionalism and the dual-liberal degree component.

Table 5
Faculty and Resources

Items	Mean	Median	Mode	SD
Do you believe that pursuing a post-graduate degree in a primary field is beneficial for graduates of ITEP?	2.95	3.00	3.00	1.32
The teaching staff is insufficient to meet the requirements of the ITEP program.	3.08	3.00	3.00	1.21
Managing both an ITEP and a 2-year B.Ed. program with the current workforce is challenging.	3.38	3.00	2.00	1.17
Do you believe that the quality of preservice teachers is influenced by the existing pool of instructors?	2.83	3.00	2.00	1.36
Overall	3.06	3.00	3.00	1.27

Table 5 of the Integrated Teacher Education Program (ITEP) shows the sentiments of teachers and resource users on several topics. The respondents' average score was 2.95, with a median and mode score of 3.00. This indicates that the respondents were predominantly neutral regarding the benefits of

obtaining a postgraduate degree in a key field for ITEP graduates. However, there is some variation in the views, as shown by the 1.32 standard deviation. The average score for the idea that the teaching staff isn't enough to meet the needs of the ITEP program is 3.08, and both the median and mode scores are also 3.00. This indicates that the majority of the respondents expressed a neutral stance, while their perspectives varied to some extent (standard deviation = 1.21). Based on a mean score of 3.38, respondents believe that it will be challenging to simultaneously handle both the ITEP and a 2-year BS program given the current workforce. The average is 2.00 and the middle value is 3.00, indicating that people's opinions vary (standard deviation = 1.17). A score of 2.83, with a median of 3.00 and a mode of 2.00, indicates uncertainty about the impact of the current group of teachers on the quality of future teachers. This shows that the respondents had a modest level of agreement, with some differences in their views (SD = 1.36). Overall, the mean score for all items is 3.06, and both the median and the mode are 3.00. This means that people have mostly neutral feelings about ITEP's faculty and resource-related parts, though their feelings do vary between things.

Table 6
Infrastructure and Resources

Items	Mean	Median	Mode	SD
The teacher education department lacks sufficient facilities to meet the needs of the ITEP program.	3.13	3.00	4.00	1.30
Accommodating 4-year integrated B.Ed. student-teachers in the teacher education department is a challenge.	3.65	4.00	5.00	1.14
Do you think that the implementation of ITEP is influenced by a lack of infrastructure?	3.95	4.00	4.00	0.75
The teacher education department lacks sufficient resources to adequately meet the ITEP needs.	3.08	3.00	5.00	1.53
Maintaining labs and associated equipment without support workers is challenging.	3.85	4.00	4.00	0.95
Do you believe that ITEP implementation is influenced by resource constraints?	3.63	4.00	4.00 ^a	1.10
Overall	3.55	4.00	4.00	1.19

The perspectives on resources and infrastructure in the Integrated Teacher Education Program (ITEP) are shown in Table 6. With a mean score of 3.13, respondents believe that the teacher education department does not have enough facilities to meet the requirements of the ITEP program. Although the mode value is 4.00, the median value of 3.00 indicates that there is some variation in the opinions held. 1.30 is the standard deviation, which measures this fluctuation. An average score of 3.65 indicates that the incorporation of 4-year Integrated B.Ed. student-teachers in the teacher education department is viewed as a challenging endeavour. The median and mode are both 4.00, suggesting moderate agreement between the respondents, with some variability in the opinions (SD = 1.14). There is a strong belief among respondents that ITEP implementation is influenced by a lack of infrastructure, as indicated by a mean score of 3.95. Both the median and the mode are at 4.00, indicating a high agreement among the respondents (SD = 0.75). Respondents are neutral that the teacher education department lacks sufficient resources to adequately meet ITEP needs, with a mean score of 3.08. The median of the data is 5.00, indicating that there is some variation in opinions. The standard deviation is 1.53. The task of managing laboratories and their equipment without the assistance of supporting staff is considered difficult, with an average rating of 3.85. The median is 4.00 and the mean is also 4.00, which shows that most of the people who answered agreed with the statement, but there was some degree of variation in their responses (standard deviation = 0.95). The people who responded to the poll also believe that limited resources affect the way ITEP is carried out, as shown by the average score of 3.63. Both the median and mean have a value of 4.00, indicating a reasonable level of

agreement between the respondents, with some variation in points of view (standard deviation = 1.10). The average score for all items combined is 3.55, with both the middle score and the most frequently occurring score at 4.00. This suggests that there is usually a modest perspective on the infrastructural and resource-related aspects of ITEP, with some variation in opinions on various issues.

Table 7
Curriculum and Program Design

Items	Mean	Median	Mode	SD
Preparing pre-service teachers with different entry and exit options is a challenging task.	4.20	4.00	4.00	0.72
Managing the regular arrival and departure of student teachers is challenging.	3.83	4.00	4.00	0.71
The selection of stage-specific speciality influences ITEP.	4.00	4.00	3.00	0.85
Designing syllabi and curriculum for primary courses at each stage of school instruction can be challenging.	2.85	3.00	1.00	1.56
Do you believe that managing many pedagogical subjects and their practices with specialized phases is a difficult task?	2.95	3.00	1.00	1.60
Effectively incorporating the ITEP curriculum into primary school courses poses a significant challenge.	2.98	3.00	4.00	1.35
Designing a curriculum that considers the specific requirements and circumstances of the local area can be challenging.	3.20	3.00	2.00	1.20
Overall	3.43	4.00	4.00	1.29

Table 7 in the Integrated Teacher Education Program (ITEP) displays the sentiments of the individuals about the content and program design. The task of providing preservice teachers with many pathways to enter and exit the profession is perceived as challenging, as shown by an average score of 4.20. Both the median and the mode are 4.00, which means that most of the people who answered agreed (SD = 0.72). Keeping track of when student teachers come and go is also considered difficult, with a mean score of 3.83. The median and mode of responses are both 4.00, indicating that a majority of the participants agreed with the statement. The standard deviation is 0.71. According to the respondents, the selection of stage-specific specializations has an impact on ITEP, as indicated by an average score of 4.00. The mode of the responses is 3.00 and the median is 4.00, indicating that the majority of respondents agreed. The standard deviation is 0.85. The average score of the respondents of 2.85 indicates uncertainty about the difficulty in developing syllabi and curricula for fundamental courses at all educational levels. The median, 3.00, deviates from the mean, 1.00, indicating that the perspectives of the individuals vary (standard deviation = 1.56). The respondent displayed a predominantly neutral attitude towards various pedagogical issues and their methods in different phases, as evidenced by a mean score of 2.95. The data set has a mode of 1.00 and a median of 3.00, indicating that there is variation in people's ideas. The standard deviation (SD) is 1.60. However, incorporating the ITEP curriculum into basic school teachings with minimal difficulty has a neutral score of 2.98. The median, 3.00, and the mode, 4.00, indicate that the majority of the respondents (SD = 1.35) agreed with the statement. Based on a mean score of 3.20, respondents perceived the school's efforts in developing a program that considers the requirements and circumstances of the local area as neutral. The data indicates that the mode is 2.00 and the median is 3.00. This suggests that most of the respondents (with a standard deviation of 1.20) had a relatively neutral opinion. The overall average score for all items is 3.43, with 4.00 being both the middle value and the most frequently occurring value. This indicates that individuals typically have moderate perspectives regarding ITEP's curriculum and program design, while there are modest variations in attitudes across different aspects.

Table 8
Financial Considerations

Items	Mean	Median	Mode	SD
ITEP is a costlier option compared to a two-year bachelor's degree in Education.	3.98	4.00	4.00	0.92
The implementation of the 4-year integrated B.Ed. The programme is challenging without the availability of additional funds.	3.92	4.00	4.00	0.83
Do you think that the quality of preservice teacher preparation is influenced by financial constraints?	4.15	4.00	5.00	1.00
Overall	4.02	4.00	4.00	0.92

Table 8, shows the responses to the integrated teacher education program (ITEP) financial issues. With an average score of 3.98, people who answered think that ITEP is more expensive than a two-year bachelor of education degree. The standard deviation is 0.92, which means that most of the people who answered agreed on many things. The median and mode have values of 4.00. The 4-year Integrated B.Ed. Program is hard to carry out because it does not have enough extra money, which is why it got an average score of 3.92. The median and mode have a value of 4, which means that most of the people who participated agreed on a modest level. The standard deviation is 0.83. Respondents strongly believe that financial constraints have a significant impact on the quality of preservice teacher preparation, as evidenced by a mean score of 4.15. The median number, 4, is close to the mode number, 5, indicating a high level of agreement among the respondents. The value of one hundred represents the standard deviation. The overall average score is 4.02. The median and mode of 4.00 indicate that the majority of individuals have a favorable perspective on ITEP regarding financial matters. Nevertheless, there are variations in individuals' perspectives on certain matters.

Table 9
Internship and School Partnerships

Items	Mean	Median	Mode	SD
ITEP needs additional schools to accommodate internship practices.	2.58	2.00	1.00	1.41
Managing internship programs at each step of school education can be challenging.	3.65	4.00	4.00	1.19
Do you believe that the quality of internship experiences is influenced by the International Test of English Proficiency (ITEP)?	2.98	3.00	4.00	1.33
Overall	3.07	3.00	4.00	1.37

Table 9 shows the perspectives on internships and school collaborations in the Integrated Teacher Education Program (ITEP). The respondents expressed disagreement with the need for new ITEP schools to facilitate internship practices. The mean score was 2.58, with a median of 2.00. The mode of 1.00 indicated a serious disagreement. The value of the standard deviation (1.41) suggests that there is a certain degree of variety in the points of view. The task of overseeing internship programs at every stage of school education is widely regarded demanding, with an average rating of 3.65. The level of agreement of the respondents appears to be reasonable, with some variety of perspectives (standard deviation = 1.19), as indicated by the median and mean values of 4.00. A mean score of 2.98 indicates that respondents had a neutral perception that the International Test of English Proficiency (ITEP) influences the quality of internship experiences. The mode is 4.00 and the median is 3.00, which shows

that people's ideas are not all the same (SD = 1.33). All of the scores put together have a mean of 3.07, with 3.00 being the middle score and 4.00 being the most common score. This shows that most people have a moderate view on the parts of internships and school cooperation in ITEP, though opinions vary a bit from subject to subject.

Table 10
Administrative Challenges

Items	Mean	Median	Mode	SD
Maintaining the many admission and exit possibilities for student teachers poses a significant challenge.	3.63	4.00	4.00	1.15
Coordinating with many departments for timetables, classes, attendance, and evaluation during the course can be challenging.	3.63	4.00	4.00	1.00
Do you think that ITEP has challenges from an administrative perspective?	2.92	3.00	2.00	1.31
Overall	3.39	3.50	4.00	1.20

Table 10 shows the points of view of administrative difficulties in the Integrated Teacher Education Program (ITEP). The task of preserving the various options for students' teachers to enter and leave is considered a notable difficulty, with an average rating of 3.63. Both the median and mean have a value of 4.00, suggesting a reasonable level of agreement among the respondents, with some variation in the points of view (standard deviation = 1.15). Collaborating with multiple departments to manage timetables, classes, attendance, and evaluation during the course is considered a difficult task, with an average score of 3.63. Both the median and mean have a value of 4.00, indicating a reasonable level of agreement among the respondents, with some variation in viewpoints (standard deviation = 1.00). The respondents have a neutral belief about the administrative issues faced by ITEP, as evidenced by a mean score of 2.92. The median value is 3.00, while the mode value is 2.00. This suggests that the opinions of the respondents have some variation, as indicated by a standard deviation of 1.31. The average score for all questions combined is 3.39, with the middle score at 3.50 and the most frequently occurring score at 4.00. This suggests that there is a generally modest view of administrative issues related to ITEP, with some variation in opinions across various items.

Table 11
Evaluation of ITEP

S.No.	Items	Mean	Median	Mode	SD
1	Do you believe that ITEP effectively trains teaching professionals of exceptional quality?	3.77	3.50	3.00	0.86
2	Do you think that the quality of pre-service teacher training is influenced by the availability of several entry and exit options?	4.00	4.00	3.00 ^a	0.85
3	The four-year duration of the ITEP program is inadequate for adequately developing high-quality preservice teachers.	3.25	3.00	2.00	1.32
4	Attaining expertise in teaching subjects within a 4-year time frame is challenging.	2.77	3.00	2.00	1.35
5	Do you believe that the limited duration of 4 years compromises the quality of the Dual-Liberal Bachelor's Degree?	2.90	3.00	1.00 ^a	1.45
6	Do you think that the quality of pre-service teachers is influenced by the ITEP curriculum?	3.60	4.00	4.00	1.10
Overall		3.38	3.00	3.00	1.25

Perceptions about the evaluation of the Integrated Teacher Education Program (ITEP) are shown in Table 11. A mean score of 3.77 indicates that respondents generally think that ITEP trains very good teachers. The mode is 3.00 and the median is 3.50, which means that most of the people who answered agreed (SD = 0.86). Respondents also believe that the quality of preservice teacher training is influenced by the availability of several entry and exit options, as indicated by a mean score of 4.00. Both the median and the mode are at 4.00, indicating high agreement among the respondents (SD = 0.85). However, there is a neutral perception that the four-year duration of the ITEP program is inadequate for adequately developing high-quality preservice teachers, with a mean score of 3.25. The median is at 3.00, while the mode is at 2.00, and the standard deviation is 1.32 indicating variation in response among respondents. A mean score of 2.77 means that the neutral answer to becoming a master in teaching subjects in 4 years is seen as hard. The median value is 3.00, the mode value is 2.00, and the standard deviation is 1.35. This shows that the responses given by the respondent were not all the same. Respondents had a neutral belief that the limited duration of 4 years compromises the quality of the Dual-Liberal Bachelor's Degree, as indicated by a mean score of 2.90. The median is at 3.00, while the mode is at 1.00, indicating some variability in opinions (SD = 1.45). Furthermore, it was found that the ITEP curriculum exerts an influence on the calibre of preservice teachers, as indicated by the respondents' mean score of 3.60 and the median and mode both have a value of 4.00, suggesting a moderate level of respondents agree with it. However, the standard deviation is 1.10 showing less consistency with the responses. The average score for all items is 3.38, with the middle score at 3.00 and the most common score at 3.00. This suggests that, in general, people have moderate perceptions about ITEP evaluation, but there is some variation in opinions on various things.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The participants held the view that ITEP offered benefits such as a reduction in the time required to prepare preservice instructors and the ability to choose their professional trajectories. However, ITEP's ability to deliver a dual liberal bachelor's degree of satisfactory quality and maintain a professional standard is items of concern. These results indicate that ITEP's coursework and program design require improvement. Concerns over faculty and resources arise as significant issues, with respondents expressing doubts about ITEP's capacity to adequately meet its needs in terms of professors and school

infrastructure. These issues might make it difficult for the program to be implemented correctly, therefore, policymakers and program administrators would need to pay attention to them. Administrative concerns are also raised, including working with other organizations and efficiently overseeing the enrollment and withdrawal of student instructors. These problems could reduce ITEP's output and influence, which would mean that its resource allocation and management practices would need to be improved. The ITEP assessment indicates that most people have positive opinions on how well it prepares teachers and offers a variety of program entry and exit routes. However, concerns over the duration of the program and its potential impact on the caliber of teacher training prior to commencement necessitate further investigation and potential modifications. The findings indicate that ITEP exhibits favorable aspects such as tailored career trajectories and reduced time allocation for preparation. However, it also faces significant challenges related to its faculty, resources, administration, and program design. Considering these issues is crucial to enhance ITEP as a program for educating prospective educators. When policymakers and managers strategize and implement educational initiatives such as ITEP, they should take into account these outcomes to ensure their continued relevance and efficacy in addressing the evolving demands of the education industry. Furthermore, further research may be necessary to examine strategies to address identified problems and improve ITEP outcomes.

REFERENCES

- Chudgar, A. (2013). Teacher labor force and Teacher Education in India: An Analysis of a Recent Policy Change and its Potential Implications. In M. Akiba (Ed.), *Teacher Reforms Around the World: Implementations and Outcomes*, International Perspectives on Education and Society, Volume 19 (pp. 55-76). Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- Hoyle, E. (2001). Teaching: prestige, status and esteem. *Educational Management Administration and Leadership*, 29(2), 139-152.
- Ministry of Education. (2020). *National Education Policy-2020*. Delhi.
- National Council for Teacher Education (NCTE). (2014). *NCTE Guidelines on Refresher Course for Teacher Educators*. New Delhi: National Council for Teacher Education.
- National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT). (1971). *Education and National Development: Report of the Education Commission 1964-66*. New Delhi: National Council of Educational Research and Training.
- Padwad, A., & Dixit, K. (2014). Continuing professional development policy 'Think Tank': An innovative experiment in India. In D. Hayes (Ed.), *Innovations in the continuing professional development of English language teachers* (pp. 249-268). London, United Kingdom: British Council.
- Sachs, J. (2003). *The Activist Teaching Profession*. Buckingham: Open University Press.